

1 **Identification of kinases and phosphatases activated by Tau expression.**

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7 We combined loss-of-function genetic approaches with a transcriptome wide network reconstruction
8 method to identify kinase and phosphatase targets controlled by expression of Tau, encoded by MAPT.
9 Candidate kinases which include enzymes that support Tau polymerization and those that function in
10 cellular processes affected by Tau synthesis included PRKCZ, CAMKV, CALM3, PRKAR2B and the cyclin
11 dependent kinase CDK5.

12 Citations

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